

Annual Report for 2018-2019

Cultivating Princeton's **Data Landscape**

THE CENTER
FOR DIGITAL
HUMANITIES
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2018-2019 CDH Year of Data

During the 2018-19 academic year, the Center for Digital Humanities launched a campus-wide initiative to encourage critical thinking about how data shapes our research, teaching and daily lives. Campus partners on this CDH initiative included faculty, staff and students in the humanities, arts, data and computer science, social science, and library and archives.

AAS / African American Studies
CITP / Center for Information Technology Policy
COS / Department of Computer Science
CSML / Center for Statistics and Machine Learning
CST / Council on Science and Technology
GSS / Gender and Sexuality Studies
OGC / Office of the General Counsel

PACM / Program in Applied and Computational Math
PICSiE / Princeton Institute for Computational Science and Engineering
PLAS / Program in Latin American Studies
PUL / Princeton University Library
UCHV / University Center for Human Values
WWS / Woodrow Wilson School of Public and International Affairs

✉ Faculty Director's Letter

What does it mean to treat poetry, brain scans and library borrowing records alike as “data”? Today, we analyze rich and complicated data produced in the humanities at scale with computational tools such as natural language processing, network analysis, and machine learning. Likewise, data scientists rely on humanists for political and historical context that helps make their work more equitable and just. During 2018-19, the Center for Digital Humanities (CDH) dedicated its energies to bringing various disciplinary voices at Princeton together to examine how data is transforming our academic fields and our society. We called this initiative “Year of Data,” and held over twenty events — lectures, symposia, conferences, workshops — with campus partners in the humanities, arts, data and computer science, social science, and library and archives.

The Year of Data engaged Princeton students and scholars in demonstrating a core CDH belief: that technology can act in the service of humanity and the humanities can enable the creation of better technology. In all of the work we do, the CDH aims to cultivate **connections** across diverse groups on campus. We raise **awareness** of cultural nuances and the implications of our increasingly data-driven world. We encourage **creativity** at the intersection of humanistic study and computational methods, and we pride ourselves on our national reputation for **best practices** in technical research and design. In the following pages it's our pleasure to share stories of select Year of Data events as well as ongoing CDH programs that best exemplify our work. We also describe two major research partnership projects the CDH launched in 2018-19 — *Derrida's Margins* and the *Princeton Prosody Archive* — that set new standards for digital humanities research and software development.

It was my own research as an English professor collecting data about historical poetics that planted the seeds for the establishment of Princeton's CDH in 2014. The success of Year of Data showcases the impact we've made in our first five years. As we rely increasingly on data in our scholarship, across Princeton's campus, and in our daily lives, the CDH will continue to advance new ideas and significant scholarship at the intersection of the humanities and technology.

Meredith Martin
Associate Professor, Department of English
Faculty Director, Center for Digital Humanities

Cultivating Connections

The CDH fosters new connections and collaborations among Princeton's divisions and disciplines, academic departments, and faculty and students.

Keynote Lecture: Safiya Noble on Algorithmic Bias

It is becoming increasingly clear, and urgent, for scholars and technologists to collectively address the problem of data bias. To facilitate these conversations at Princeton, the CDH invited Safiya Noble (Associate Professor, UCLA, Departments of Information Studies and African American Studies; Visiting Faculty, University of Southern California, Annenberg School of Communication and Journalism), author of *Algorithms of Oppression: How Search Engines Reinforce Racism*, to deliver our Year of Data keynote lecture. Noble described her decade-long research into the complex interplay of algorithms, operating systems, human input and market pressures that influence the technical design of today's most prevalent online tools, and urged us to think philosophically and ethically about the human elements of data science.

Noble spoke to a standing-room-only crowd of students, faculty and campus leaders from such diverse programs as African American Studies, the Program in Applied and Computational Mathematics, the Princeton University Library, the Department of Computer Science, the Humanities Council, and the Council on Information Technology Policy. Her talk encouraged the Princeton community to put our intellectual and social energies into addressing the inequality that is perpetuated by technological advancement, and fostered ongoing critical discussions about how data shapes our research, teaching and daily lives.

Faculty Seminar: Telling Stories with Data

How is data-driven scholarship transforming the research of Princeton's renowned humanities scholars? How can humanists use computational methods to mobilize their research to uncover the richness of their research material? These were some of the questions motivating the 2018-19 Humanities Council Gilburne Faculty Seminar, "Telling Stories with Data," moderated by CDH Faculty Director Meredith Martin (Associate Professor, English).

This interdisciplinary group of professors met monthly to think broadly and across disciplines about their approaches to all kinds of data through all manner of storytelling: big, small, ubiquitous, hidden. They shared their research and welcomed guests such as a *Wall Street Journal* pioneer in computer-assisted reporting and a developer behind the complicated interface for *Global Forest Watch*. From medical records to musical scores, the group learned from one another how data from myriad disciplines was marshaled to tell new stories about humanity.

Unsolved Data Problems

The CDH collaborated with the Department of Computer Science and the Center for Statistics and Machine Learning to bring humanists and computer and data scientists together to address the challenges that arise when humanities material is transformed into data and code. Marina Rustow (Professor, Near Eastern Studies and History), Meredith Martin (Associate Professor, English), and Dan Trueman (Professor, Music) shared how new possibilities in humanities research — such as large-scale digitization, curating and sharing vast amounts of metadata, optical character recognition (OCR) and experimental audio engineering — have created a host of new issues that require creative technical and scholarly solutions. Jennifer Rexford (Professor, Computer Science and Engineering) moderated group discussion as audience members proposed possible alternatives and solutions.

Above Safiya Noble (UCLA & USC) speaks to a standing-room-only crowd on algorithmic accountability.

Below Dan Trueman (Music) speaks to the Princeton data science community on emerging digital research for musicians and musicologists.

Humanities Council Gilburne Faculty Seminar Participants

Ruha Benjamin
Department of African American Studies

Joao Biehl
Department of Anthropology

Janet Chen
Department of History, East Asian Studies

Angela Creager
Department of History, History of Science

Eve Krakowski
*Department of Near Eastern Studies,
Judaic Studies*

Nicole Legnani
Department of Spanish and Portuguese

Susan Marshall
Lewis Center for the Arts, Dance

Meredith Martin
*Department of English,
Center for Digital Humanities*

Anna Shields
Department of East Asian Studies

Joe Stephens
Program in Journalism, Humanities Council

Dmitri Tymoczko
Department of Music

Moulie Vidas
Department of Religion, Judaic Studies

Autumn Womack
*Department of African American Studies,
Department of English*

Cultivating Connections

Data Conversations

Princeton's humanities scholars are increasingly relying on data and computational analysis in their research and teaching. In the CDH-sponsored series called "Data Conversations," faculty and graduate students hold informal discussions in their academic departments about what data means for their research and disciplines as a whole.

Data Conversations for 2018-19 took place in the English and History departments. In History, CDH Postgraduate Research Associate (PGRA) Sean Fraga (Ph.D. '18) brought together Rhae Lynn Barnes (Assistant Professor) and fellow CDH PGRA Jessica Mack (Ph.D. '18) to reflect on how digital humanities practices align with the expanding interest in public history. In English, Joshua Kotin (Associate Professor) and Meredith Martin (Associate Professor) discussed their CDH collaborations, *The Shakespeare and Company Project* and the *Princeton Prosody Archive*. Graduate student project managers Elspeth Green (Ph.D. '18) and Mary Naydan (Ph.D. expected '21) discussed the scholarly practice of data curation and the intellectual challenges of learning web design.

Left Mary Naydan and Elspeth Green speak at an English department installment of the "Data Conversations" series.

Programs for Graduate Students

A major priority for the CDH is creating community among Princeton graduate students who are engaging in digital humanities research in different departments. In the spring of 2019 the CDH welcomed its first cohort of Graduate Fellows in Digital Humanities. The ten fellows met monthly to learn about one another's projects, which covered a range of subjects, including conceptions of race, gender and resistance across cultures; 20th-century French music; and ancient Chinese texts. Graduate students were able to expand their digital humanities training with the support of CDH travel grants to attend summer schools throughout the world.

The CDH also serves to connect humanities graduate students with opportunities after they leave Princeton. We led a special session of the Graduate School's "Pathways with a Ph.D." series called "DH Jobs, On and Off the Tenure Track," where recent Ph.D.s with various digital humanities jobs discussed the opportunities, challenges and realities of the ever-changing academic market.

Right Rebecca Munson (CDH) and Anne Cheng (English & American Studies) reflect on the classroom as a "lab" space in a joint event with the McGraw Center for Teaching and Learning.

CDH Graduate Fellows in the Digital Humanities

Teaching and Pedagogy

As technology and computational methods transform humanities scholarship, they also impact Princeton's teaching mission. Since its establishment, the CDH has been a campus leader in helping students and teachers think critically about the role of technology and data in the learning experience.

Our "Introduction to Digital Humanities" course, taught in fall 2018 by CDH Weld Postdoctoral Fellow Nora Benedict (Assistant Professor, University of Georgia), introduced undergraduates to key topics in digital humanities from a global perspective. Students worked through the foundations of the field while also exploring issues of access, maintenance and care for digital projects in regions with technological constraints. Students delved into primary sources in the Princeton University Library's Rare Books and Special Collections, using material from the Digital Archive of Latin American and Caribbean Ephemera to gather data, which they then transformed with various software, platforms and databases.

During Year of Data, the CDH partnered with the McGraw Center for Teaching and Learning on a panel discussion called "Lab Learning in the Humanities and Social Sciences," where CDH Project and Education Coordinator Rebecca Munson highlighted how digital humanities projects facilitate experimentation and collaboration and can serve as an alternative learning space.

2019 Graduate Fellows in Digital Humanities

- Kimberly Bain**
English and Interdisciplinary Humanistic Study
- Ipsita Dey**
Anthropology
- Yangyou Fang**
Spanish and Portuguese
- Peter Kitlas**
Near Eastern Studies
- Dylan Principi**
Music
- Gian Rominger**
East Asian Studies
- Deborah Schlein**
Near Eastern Studies
- Kristen Starkowski**
English
- Serena Stein**
Anthropology
- Ray Thornton**
History

Cultivating Awareness

The CDH serves as a space for critical discussions about data, technology and the human experience both in the academy and in the public sphere.

Workshop participants in the JUST DATA lab explore the effects of privilege through the mechanics of table-top games.

JUST DATA Lab

By rethinking and retooling data for justice, scholars can find powerful ways to leverage research and teaching for advocacy. As part of the Year of Data, sociologist and CDH Faculty Fellow Ruha Benjamin (Associate Professor, African American Studies) gathered a group of activists, artists, educators and researchers at the CDH for the JUST DATA Lab. The goal of this hands-on pedagogy workshop was to develop a humanistic approach to data conception, production and circulation as part of the broader movement for black lives. By examining and critiquing datasets related to housing and economic justice, policing and abolition, and public health and environmental justice, lab participants developed teaching material that can be adapted for a range of classrooms and communities.

Public Humanities

Lavar Edmonds (Research Specialist, Sociology) presents his work with the Eviction Lab (evictionlab.org/about).

The CDH plays a key role in campus conversations about public humanities, and fosters new initiatives for digitally inflected public-facing scholarship. We are a proud sponsor of the Campus Iconography Committee's "(In)Visible Princeton" project, which uses augmented reality (AR) to highlight lesser-known aspects of Princeton's

history in a series of themed campus walking tours. The tours, on topics such as African American life or women at Princeton, include interpretive text and supplemental media, such as images, audio and video. By elevating these stories, the tours cultivate awareness of the nuanced history of Princeton.

Cultivating Awareness

Who Counts? A Symposium on Intersectional Data

The creation and use of data are never neutral. Rather than taking data as self-evident, “Who Counts? A Symposium on Intersectional Data” focused on the gaps, blanks and absences in data practices. Featured speakers Lauren Klein (Associate Professor, Departments of English and Quantitative Theory & Methods, Emory University) and Mimi Onuoha (Class of 2011), an artist and researcher, highlighted how data is dependent upon existing power structures, and challenged the audience to imagine how educators and scholars might minimize inequalities in data collection, analysis and visualization.

Klein and Onuoha reminded us that since data informs policy decisions, working to combat data bias has immediate real-world implications. They urged caution and compassion when collecting data on marginalized groups due to harmful consequences of negative attention on vulnerable populations. Examining who benefits, and therefore “who counts,” is a goal to which we as a community can contribute in our research, our classrooms and our everyday interactions.

“Every missing dataset is benefiting someone by not existing.” —Mimi Onuoha

Left Onuoha (Class of 2011) and Klein (Emory) describe how data practices have increasingly replicated existing inequalities and institutionalized bias across the country.

Below A packed house attending “A Symposium on Intersectional Data,” where Klein presented work from her forthcoming book, *Data Feminism*.

Building Bridges with Data

2017-19 CDH Weid Postdoctoral Fellow Nora Benedict (University of Georgia) delivers opening remarks at “Building Bridges with Data,” a conference she organized.

Understanding the ethical dimensions of working with archival collections—both print and digital—is increasingly relevant in times of political and social upheaval. How do we access, create and maintain archives for global change? How do we build transcontinental bridges across cultures and institutions through a shared interest in archival data?

To address these questions, the CDH hosted “Building Bridges with Data,” a day-long symposium that brought together archivists, historians, literary scholars, librarians and digital humanities scholars. The event generated crucial discussions about the ways that archives and data can enable unique networks of collaboration and communication in the 21st century.

cdh.princeton.edu @PrincetonDH @PrincetonCDH

BUILDING BRIDGES WITH DATA

SPEAKERS/PARTICIPANTS

- ALBERTO MANGUEL**
Former Director of the National Library of Argentina
- FERNANDO ACOSTA-RODRIGUEZ**
Librarian for Latin American Studies, Latino Studies, and Iberian Peninsular Studies
Princeton University
- GABRIELLE WINKLER**
Special Collections Assistant for the Latin American
Ephemera Collection
Princeton University
- ALEX GIL**
Digital Scholarship Librarian
Columbia University Libraries
- FRANCESCA GIANNETTI**
Digital Humanities Librarian
Rutgers University
- LUIZA WAINER**
Metadata Librarian, Spanish/Portuguese Specialty
Princeton University
- MARCY SCHWARTZ**
Professor of Spanish
Rutgers University
- RUBÉN GALLO**
Walter S. Carpenter, Jr., Professor in Language,
Literature, and Civilization of Spain
Princeton University
- JESSICA MACK**
Postgraduate Research Associate in History
and Digital Humanities
Princeton University
- NORA BENEDICT**
Postdoctoral Fellow in the Center for Digital Humanities
Princeton University
- ROB KARL**
Assistant Professor of History
Princeton University

How do we build transcontinental bridges across cultures and institutions through a shared interest in archival data?

FRIDAY, APRIL 12
8:30 a.m. - 5:30 p.m.
CENTER FOR DIGITAL HUMANITIES
Firestone Library
B Floor

Co-sponsored by:
Department of Spanish & Portuguese
Digital Humanities
Program in Latin American Studies
Princeton University Library

Cultivating Creativity

The CDH encourages exploration and originality in approaching data, technology and ideas.

Freshman Seminar: Weird Data

“Weird Data,” a freshman seminar taught by CDH Perkins Postdoctoral Fellow Jim Casey and sponsored by the Center for Statistics and Machine Learning, provided a wide-ranging introduction to the world of data in all its forms, ideas and peculiarities. An exercise that gave students an alternative way to interpret datasets asked them to produce their own “data cuisine.” Using everyday condiments and candy, students

defined, categorized and classified data based on sensory experience.

One group of students transformed a dataset about the intergenerational effects of education using jelly beans. With sweet jelly beans representing gains in education, and sour standing for decrease, the students “computed” data trends through nuances of taste.

Students use jelly beans to represent a dataset of educational outcomes through taste.

How can the sensory experiences of food—taste, texture, smell—provide embodied ways to explore data?

Above The user interface of *Derrida's Margins*, built by the CDH, allows readers to browse rich metadata about Jacques Derrida's annotations.

Left Header graphics provide a sample of the marginalia, bookmarks and notes now available at derridas-margins.princeton.edu.

Derrida's Margins

The *Derrida's Margins* project, created by the CDH Development and Design Team in collaboration with Katie Chenoweth (Associate Professor, French and Italian), leverages user experience design to help scholars investigate philosopher Jacques Derrida's theories of deconstruction. Providing high-quality digital images and rich encoding of the marginalia from books in Derrida's personal research library, held by Princeton University's Rare Books and Special Collections, visitors can explore Derrida's reading process through the sticky notes, bookmarks, calendar pages, index cards, correspondence and notes he left behind in his books.

The site's design intentionally extends Derrida's theories into interactive media. Elements such as space, typography and color were chosen based on principles of postmodern design; the fluidity between their form and content provokes users and creates space for playful interpretation. The richly interactive website seeks to break down boundaries between users, site creators and the site's content. By exploring *Derrida's Margins*, visitors experience the complex interplay of texts, markings and references that were the core of Derrida's thought.

Cultivating Creativity

Latin American Ephemera Hackathon

New insights into Princeton University Library data emerged when research software engineers and programmers from around campus gathered at the CDH to “hack” the library’s Digital Archive of Latin American and Caribbean Ephemera. Using metadata from this multilingual collection of over 12,000 items, participants experimented with named entity recognition, classification, automated image processing, topic modeling and data visualization. The event demonstrated how computational methods can be used to better understand and expose the richness of our library collections.

CDH Developer Nick Budak guides graduate students Miranda Marraccini (Ph.D. '19, English) and Deborah Schlein (Ph.D. '19, Near Eastern Studies) in a “Playing with Data” workshop.

Playing with Data

The CDH collaborated with the Council on Science and Technology (CST) on a workshop series called “Playing with Data” that introduced

the principles and tools of creative coding. Participants explored various datasets, and were encouraged to think beyond conventional modes of visualization toward more evocative, effective ways of representing data.

Data Physicalization

With a goal of moving beyond conventional modes of data visualization, the CDH has been experimenting with data physicalization to explore, analyze and make arguments with data. Through 3D modeling software and printing, data becomes a physical object that can be held in the hand and viewed from multiple angles. Some of our recent work—such as weaving created out of data from *Derrida’s Margins* or origami representations of the membership history of the Shakespeare and Company Lending Library—add spatial, tactile and temporal dimensions to the data we have created. The sensory experience invites new audiences to surface rich and unexpected narratives that would otherwise be hidden.

Above The 3D models demonstrate the advantages of three dimensions for representing data: time series data is displayed with sequential months and years adjacent to each other, which makes it easier to discern seasonal and annual trends.

Inset The origami comprises two intersecting shapes to represent the ratio of library activity by notable (cube) and relatively unknown members (octahedron). By holding this piece in two different ways, participants can “grasp” the two sets of data.

Bottom left The tapestry invokes the metaphor of weaving as writing by embodying Derrida’s intertextuality. Viewers become participants, and weave based on a pattern generated from the data.

Bottom right User Experience Designer Gissoo Doroudian, weaving chapter one.

Cultivating Best Practices

The CDH defines standards, guidelines and procedures for rigorous digital humanities scholarship.

Dataset Curation

The CDH's annual Dataset Curation Grants provide key support for Princeton researchers who use humanities data in their work. Recipients receive expert training in the emerging tools and techniques of data curation, and are taught best practices in data selection, gathering, modeling, cleaning, transformation and maintenance. By producing research datasets suitable for computational analysis, grantees contribute to a portfolio of humanities datasets ripe for collaboration with the Princeton data science community.

In 2018-19, datasets selected for funding included a comprehensive portrait of 4th-century burial practices across England; a digital edition of the official, 6,000-page history of the Tang Dynasty written in the 11th century; a study of the 6th-century Justinianic plague linking everything from rat bones to gravestone epitaphs; a database tracking the narrative evolution of Ethiopian "miracle" tales about the Virgin Mary between the 14th and 20th centuries; and an examination of over 800,000 tobacco industry documents that asks how menthol cigarettes were marketed as a "healthy" alternative across the 20th century.

XML transcription of a library lending card belonging to Gertrude Stein. These 2019-20 Dataset Curation Grant recipients worked to extract and enrich data from Sylvia Beach's personal collection of documents for inclusion in the CDH-sponsored *Shakespeare and Company Project*.


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      <name>(Villa des Oliviers,</name><settlement>Nice)</settlement>
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      </bibl>
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2018-19 CDH Consultations

Consultations

39
The number of different University departments participating in CDH consultations.

Each year, the CDH sees more than 100 students, faculty and staff for consultations about developing digital humanities research, courses or careers. With staff expertise in a variety of disciplinary and technological fields, the CDH is able to provide guidance to scholars from various departments and in disparate stages of digital humanities work. Consultations often serve as the initial seeds of fruitful projects for senior theses, dissertations or CDH research partnerships.

Library's collections to be part of the campus data landscape, and discussed options for integrating library data into the cutting-edge data-driven scholarship at Princeton.

20
The number of DH subfields represented in CDH consultations.

Collections as Data

Libraries, archives and museums around the world are making their collections available for computationally driven research. During the Year of Data, the CDH's monthly reading group centered on the topic of "Collections as Data." By bringing together librarians, archivists, CDH staff and Princeton researchers, the group foregrounded the potential for Princeton University

CDH Developer Benjamin Hicks guides graduate students, including Wafa Isfahani (M.A. '19, Near Eastern Studies), in a "Playing with Data" workshop.

Cultivating Best Practices

Princeton Prosody Archive

During the Year of Data, the CDH launched a redesigned version of its flagship project, the *Princeton Prosody Archive* (PPA). A full-text searchable database of thousands of digitized books in English published between 1570 and 1923, the PPA collects historical documents and highlights discourses about the study of language and poetry.

The PPA not only contributes to the field of historical poetics, but also sets standards for digital humanities publication and software development practices. The site has copious documentation that clearly lets users know how the site is organized for ease of use and citation. All project contributors—editorial, technical and administrative—are credited for their work. As a true scholarly project, the site contains editorial essays that describe how the PPA can be used for teaching and research.

PRINCETON
PROSODY
ARCHIVE

The PPA represents the very best of software development practices, boasting a code base that is open source, tested, documented and citable. All key technical aspects—including site architecture, data models and code documentation—are freely available for fellow technologists to reproduce and modify for their own work.

Contributors and board members celebrating the launch of the *Princeton Prosody Archive*. From left to right: Rebecca Sutton Koeser (CDH), Meagan Wilson (Ithaca S+R), Virginia Jackson (UC Irvine), Rebecca Munson (CDH), Nick Budak (CDH), Colette Johnson (Ithaca S+R), Meredith McGill (Rutgers), Meredith Martin (English, CDH), Mary Naydan (English), Yopie Prins (Michigan) and Jeff Strabone (Connecticut College).

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Copy edited by:
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Printed and bound by Brilliant Graphics
Exton, PA, USA

September 2019

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3374003

